

1 **Sp110 loss functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Sp110 modulation in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in
11 *Homo sapiens*.

12 Citations

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